

SOP Title	Taking stool samples and rectal swabs for TRACS-Liverpool study		
Version	1	SOP reference	TRACS_SOP_003
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Introduction

The TRACS-Liverpool (Tracking AMR Across Care Settings in Liverpool) study aims to track transmission of extended-spectrum beta lactamase and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (ESBL-E/CPE) in hospitals and care homes in Liverpool. We will do this by recruiting care home residents and hospital patients and collecting stool and associated environmental samples over a period of months. By testing these samples for ESBL-E/CPE organisms and using gene sequencing techniques to track bacteria we hope to identify where transmission of resistant bacteria is happening. We then aim to combine this information with routine data on antibiotic usage and patterns of care and will work with the hospital flow teams and participating care homes to co-design and pilot interventions to block transmission and, ultimately, reduce the number of drug-resistant infections.

1. Purpose

This method is applicable to the taking of stool samples and rectal swabs associated with the TRACS-Liverpool Study.

2. Responsibilities

- Collection team
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Recording barcodes and relevant participant data in RedCap software.
- Laboratory staff
 - Receive samples from collection team and complete sample collection log

3. Definitions and Abbreviations

TRACS	Tracking AMR Across Care Settings
LSTM	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
ESBL-E	Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase-producing Enterobacterales

4. Related Documents

TRACS_SOP_004	Environmental swab processing
TRACS_SOP_002	Staff hand sampling
TRACS_SOP_005	Stool sample processing
Risk Assessment for Work with Hazardous Biological Agent_TRACS	Risk assessment

5. Risk Assessment

<i>Hazard (Cause and Consequence)</i>	<i>Affected Groups</i>	<i>Existing controls (e.g., PPE...)</i>
<i>Biological Hazards</i>		
Rectal swabs and stool samples swabs: potential infection	Collection team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wear PPE (gloves and apron) when handling swabs/samples. For spills on site, refer to local guidance. For spills on transport to the laboratory refer to section 7.3
<i>Chemical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A
<i>Physical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A

6. Sample Collection/Workflow

6.1 Study outline

Collect stool samples/rectal swabs from consented patients outlined in TRACS study protocol and deliver to LSTM lab for processing.

6.2 Recording swab data

Use RedCap software to record all data.

7. Procedure

7.1 Equipment and Reagents

7.1.1 Consumables required

Materials	Company/Code
Gloves	Starlabs/SG-C-(sizw: S, M, L)
Flocked Swabs	Sterilin/300-0224
30ml Faeces Container with attached spoon	Greiner/443103
Clear storage bags	Fisher/BAJ-340-091N
Transport box	Sarstedt/95.1720

7.2 Stool sample collection

1. Where possible collect stool from a clean (uncontaminated) sample collected using a paper stool collection device.
2. Using the spoon from the collection pot put a minimum walnut sized amount into the pot.

3. Ensure lid is attached securely. Place labelled pot into plastic bag and seal.
4. Record the sample data by scanning QR code on sample sticker into participant record on RedCap.

5. Transport samples to the LSTM laboratory and store at 4°C until processing according to TRACS_SOP_005

7.3 Rectal swab collection

1. Don appropriate PPE (gloves and apron)
2. Explain the procedure to the participant including showing them the swab to be used.
3. Ensure the participant is comfortable and that you will not be disturbed. Offer a chaperone and, if requested, do not proceed until they are present.
4. Ensure participant is covered with only bottom exposed as necessary. Check that anal area does not have broken skin or be otherwise sore or soiled. Do NOT use lubricant jelly as this will affect the swab result.
5. Remove swab by gently twisting cap; if seal appears to be broken use a fresh, sealed swab.
6. Hold swab with thumb and forefinger over the red score line, to prevent accidental snapping of swab (see picture).

7. Insert swab into rectum, approximately 3-5cm (1-2 inches) past the anus and **very gently** rotate clockwise for approximately 5 seconds.
8. Gently withdraw swab and place immediately into the tube, making sure it does not touch any other surfaces.
9. Ensure participant is dressed and comfortable, thank them!
10. Remove gloves and apron. Wash hands.
11. Ensure swab is labelled including date/time.
12. Record the sample data by scanning QR code on sample sticker into participant record on Redcap.
13. Transport samples to the LSTM laboratory and store at 4°C until processing according to TRACS_SOP_005

7.4 Spill procedure

In the unlikely event of a spill occurring, follow local guidelines for how to clean up. If samples are spilt/opened during transport to the laboratory, cross contamination may have occurred. Any open swab tubes will be transferred to a class II microbiological safety cabinet and dealt with according to laboratory SOPs. The details will be recorded, and a decision made by a senior member of the lab team whether to process the samples or discard them.

8. Review History

19/08/24 - Reviewed and no changes needed.